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Willingness to pay for the environment : the role of social status and of prosocial orientation*

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Abstract

Based on the 2020 International Social Survey Program (ISSP) IV Environment Module, this paper examines how individual characteristics influence the willingness to pay to protect the environment. We contribute to the literature by highlighting the role of social status: the higher respondents place themselves on the social scale, the more they are willing to pay; and of prosocial orientation: the more willing respondents are to take action for the environment independently of others, the more they are willing to pay. We underline that the impact of social status, i.e., respondents' subjective perception of their position on the social scale, remains significant even after controlling for income and education levels. Our results suggest that, in order to strengthen individuals' willingness to pay for the environment, two types of policies may be effective: (1) policies aimed at influencing subjective social status and its determinants –for example, exposing professional groups to narratives framing their position as socially valued, reducing perceived inequalities, enhancing individuals' sense of control over life events, and fostering orientation toward long-term planning; and (2) policies aimed at shaping prosocial orientation, that is, convincing individuals that personal actions are meaningful even when they are not widely adopted by others. Besides, based on our results, climate policies can be successful when imposing net costs on the following groups: individuals who rank themselves in the top 40% of the population (social status); the 50% of individuals who agree to act without waiting for others to do so (prosocial orientation). By contrast, climate policies that impose net costs on the complementary segments of the population are likely to face disapproval.

Keywords: willingness to pay, valuation of environmental effects, government environmental policy, preferences, ecological transition.

JEL Classification: D12, D91, Q51, Q58

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1 Introduction

Economic analysis is accustomed to focusing on individuals who are willing to pay for goods or services that provide direct and private utility (buying food, clothes, insurance contracts, etc.); however, explaining the willingness to pay for goods or services that yield indirect and public utility has received comparatively less attention. Environmental externalities typically fall into the latter category. The private benefits from environmental quality depend on others' actions; moreover, these benefits are long-term and uncertain. In that context, what are the factors that drive "pro-environmental" behaviors?

Environmental protection has become a very important factor in political decision-making in recent years. The deterioration caused by human activities is now recognized, as is the need for adaptation (Rockstrom et al., 2009). The most visible consequences are climate change and natural disasters, but they are not the only ones: biodiversity is declining, soil and water are being polluted, and so on (Richardson et al., 2023). To achieve transition towards a sustainable economy, individuals should adapt their consumption, standards of living, and consent to taxation. However, there is opposition to certain actions in this direction due to the immediate costs they entail (Fairbrother, 2022). Furthermore, since countries are neither affected to the same extent nor equally responsible for past and present carbon emissions, support for climate policies varies significantly across regions (Anderson et al., 2017). It is generally acknowledged that the bulk of the effort should stem from firms' production mode and from governments' rules and taxation (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022)¹, however, individuals also have a role to play (Pisani-Ferry and Mahfouz, 2023) and they can complement collective action. Given the stakes for both humanity and the planet (Steffen et al., 2015), it is thus vital to analyse the factors that motivate individuals to support pro-environmental actions.

Whereas willingness to pay (hereafter WTP) has received both theoretical and empirical attention in the scientific literature, we will focus on the empirical application of WTP for the environment. Generally, it is measured through a survey question aiming at capturing the degree to which individuals are willing to pay for an environmental good ("green product") or service (reducing pollution, etc.); to pay taxes devoted to protecting the environment or mitigating climate change (carbon tax, etc.); or the degree to which they stand ready to cut down their standards of living in order to protect the environment. What are the main factors proven to impact the most WTP for the environment? The level of education has a positive effect (Tianyu and Meng, 2020; Meyer, 2015). Income is also positively related with WTP for the environment. However the relation is more complex, as a reversal occurs for the very top income (Shao et al., 2018), and because the inequality in income distribution may have a role to play (Baumgärtner et al., 2017). The degree to which individuals feel concerned about environmental problems (Bamberg and Möser, 2007), or the extent to which they think it is a concern for their country (Shao et al., 2018), are also important. Finally, several socio-demographic variables have been studied. Age (Tianyu and Meng, 2020), gender (Dardanoni and

¹See the Summary for Policymakers, sections C.4-C.7 for the productive system, and sections E.3-E.4 for governments' actions.

Guerriero, 2021), political and religious orientation (Davidovic et al., 2020; Zemo and Nigus, 2021), urban or rural domicile (An et al., 2024), being single or in couple (Ligus, 2018), having children or not (Joung et al., 2014), have all shown an impact on WTP for the environment, at least in specific countries or local case studies.

Interestingly, two variables have been under-studied in economic research about the WTP for the environment. First, Social Status can have a role to play. Independently of an "objective" social status based on income or education, a "subjective" social status, i.e., where individuals place themselves within a social "ladder", can influence their willingness to pay. In socio-psychological literature, for example, it has been shown that, controlling for education and income, middle class households are more likely to engage in pro-environmental actions (Chen, 2023). Second, Prosocial attitude can also matter for the WTP for the environment. Prosocial attitudes encompass a wide range of attitudes, which common point is that they entail a utility *per se*, an intrinsic motivation that does not bring a direct utility from material consumption or revenue (Bénabou and Tirole, 2006). The canonical example would be a benevolent participation in a charity association. But pro-environmental actions also typically fall into that definition: acting, or paying, for the environment can have value to an individual, even if there is a majority of people not acting against an environmental externality. In that case, a prosocial attitude will positively influence the WTP for the environment. This is why we choose to focus on social status and on prosocial attitude in our study.

To do so, we use the ISSP (International Social Survey Programme) data. This international survey includes several questions about the willingness to pay for the environment. We use the most recent (2023) published wave of the survey, with responses collected in 2021. It includes 28 countries. Most responses are coded on a Likert scale (e.g. from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree"). Our dependent variable, willingness to pay (WTP), is based on three questions. The question: "To what extent would you be prepared to pay much higher prices to protect the environment?" is used as a baseline. The other two ("To what extent would you be prepared to pay much higher taxes to protect the environment?" and "To what extent would you be prepared to accept reductions in your standard of living to protect the environment?") are used as variants. The WTP is then explained by the factors put forward in the previous literature, and by our two variables of interest. First, Subjective Social Status is built from responses to: "In our society, there are groups which tend to be towards the top and groups which tend to be towards the bottom. Where would you put yourself on this scale?". Respondents have to choose their position in a 10-point scale from 1-the lowest to 10-the top. Second, in our context, the prosocial attitude is measured through responses to the following statement: "There is no point in doing what I can for the environment unless others do the same". Respondents had to express their degree of agreement to that statement. We assume that individuals who derive intrinsic motivation from acting for the environment (i.e., prosocially inclined individuals) are more likely to respond "strongly disagree," as their intrinsic utility from contributing outweighs the perceived personal cost of the action. Conversely, more individualistic respondents—whose utility depends on oth-

ers' efforts to reduce the negative externality—are expected to agree with the statement to a greater extent. Let us now turn to the methodology. Because most variables are ordinal, we chose to analyse the determinants of the WTP with an ordered logit model. However, the standard ordered logit relies on the proportional odds (or parallel lines) assumption, which implies that the estimated effect of each explanatory variable is identical across all response thresholds. For example, the probability of answering “very willing to pay” increases by the same coefficient when income rises from “low” to “middle,” or from “middle” to “high.” To relax this restrictive assumption, we use a Partial Proportional Odds Model (PPOM), which allows some coefficients to vary across thresholds while maintaining proportionality for others (Peterson and Harrell, 1990). For example, the probability of answering “very willing to pay” may change differently when comparing “low” with “middle” income and when comparing “middle” with “high” income. This approach provides greater flexibility and ensures that the model accurately reflects the structure of our ordinal data.

Our main result is that subjective social status and prosocial attitudes do have an impact on the willingness to pay for the environment. We show that, controlling for income and education, a higher social status implies a higher willingness to pay. Our interpretation is as follows: comparing two individuals with comparable education level and income, an individual that places himself high on the social scale is more willing to pay for the environment than an individual that places himself low on the social scale. Next, we show that prosocial attitudes favor willingness to pay for the environment. These results hold after controlling for the other usual variables from the literature, like the degree of environmental concern, gender, age, etc.

Thus, our paper contributes to the literature in several ways. First, we shed light on under-studied variables, subjective social status and prosocial inclination. Second, we contribute to the interdisciplinarity, by bridging socio-psychological literature with economics literature. Third, we use a more recent survey than in the reviewed literature. Fourth, we provide an international analysis of the willingness to pay, whereas most articles are country-based or local case-studies. Fifth, our analysis provides a concrete lever for transition policies. Indeed, some important variables highlighted in the literature are difficult, costly, or slow to act upon. For example, education and income may take time to improve in a given society, as well as reducing income inequality. In contrast, the subjective social status can be affected through communication (exposing professional groups to narratives framing their position as socially valued, reducing perceived inequalities, enhancing individuals' sense of control over life events, and fostering orientation toward long-term planning); and prosocial orientation can be regularly fostered by governmental or non-governmental campaigns that emphasize the meaningfulness of individual actions, even when they are not widely adopted by others, and that promote norms such as the idea that everyone must “do their part” or “do the right thing”. Given that transition policies must be implemented rapidly in light of the urgency of climate change, it may be relevant to combine long-term strategies (which remain necessary) with short-term communication or incentive campaigns. By highlighting the role of subjective social status and prosocial orientation in individuals' willingness to pay for the environment, we

therefore identify concrete short-term levers for the design of effective transition policies. Besides, our study identifies which segments of the population are more likely to support climate policies, and which are more likely to disapprove of them. Based on our results, climate policies can be successful when imposing net costs on the following groups: individuals who rank themselves in the top 40% of the population in terms of social status; and the 50% of individuals who agree to act without waiting for others to do so (prosocial orientation). Control variables further indicate that imposing a net cost on the top 40% of the income distribution is associated with positive, or at worst neutral, support². By contrast, imposing net costs on the complementary segments of the population is likely to face disapproval or political opposition.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature. Section 3 presents the data and the method. Section 4 presents and discusses the main results. Section 5 provides robustness checks. Section 6 concludes.

2 Literature review

The collective action needed to implement the climate transition is the responsibility of collective actors: governments and international entities, and firms. However, individuals can play their part. As an example, some socially questionable products have been banned to reflect changes in global consumer behavior (Zatoński et al., 2020). Furthermore, individual support for transition policies is an important matter for democratic countries. The concept of willingness to pay (WTP) is well adapted to capture such political acceptance.

In a nutshell, the theoretical literature uses the WTP when there are no markets and no prices to express a demand for a given service or product. More precisely, it is "the value an agent is willing to pay for a change in the level of production of a given externality, a way of putting a monetary value on an individual preference." (Andan et al., 1995). This monetary representation can be criticized (Kanya et al., 2019), but it allows comparability and is straightforward to interpret. We thus chose to use it in this article. The higher the WTP of a given individual, the higher its support for transition policies. Using theoretical models of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation with social image (Bénabou and Tirole, 2003, 2006, 2025), this support can be analyzed through components of an agent's utility function. The agent will provide a pro-environmental action (e.g. a high WTP) depending on: the level of personal cost of the action for the environment (paying more, being taxed more, cutting standards of living); on the intrinsic motivation (either the private benefits from reducing the negative environmental externality, or the pure pleasure of contributing to a valorised cause); on the benefits from others providing the pro-environmental action; and on the reputation or social image of this action.

Turning to empirical applications of the willingness to pay for the environment, the literature presents two main approaches to measure it. First, some studies are based on market behaviors. In finance, a "green premium" is an additional cost, i.e. a higher price or a lesser return, that investors accept to pay in order to buy assets related to sustainable projects or firms

²As for education, any increase in the level of education has a positive effect.

(Ferraro et al., 2005; Chen et al., 2023). In the goods and services markets, studies proxy the willingness to pay by the use of ecolabels, or admittedly environmental-friendly products. The consumer arbitrage is difficult because these products are generally more expensive than their non-green competitors (Xu et al., 2012; Duckworth et al., 2022). It can be organic food, clothing with recycled raw materials, electrical car (Qiao and Dowell, 2022; Poder and He, 2017; Sörqvist et al., 2013). Second, another method to proxy the willingness to pay is to create experiments, to ask directly, or to test it. It is, for example, used in studies about paying for protecting an endangered species or reducing air pollution (Sun et al., 2016; Jacobsen and Hanley, 2009; Broberg and Brännlund, 2008). Questions about the consent to taxes also use these methods. Climate policies imply financing major changes in society in the energy or infrastructure sectors (Szulecki et al., 2016; Jordan and Huitema, 2014), which may require to raise new dedicated taxes, thus willingness to pay taxes can proxy the degree of support for climate policies (Kallbekken et al., 2011; Fabre et al., 2025). In this "qualitative" willingness to pay literature, there is a consensus that Choice-Based Conjoint questions are the best proxy (Miller et al., 2011). This method reveals a declared willingness to pay that is hypothetical and indirect and, therefore, less precise, but more reliable than other declarative methods. Another recognized method are situation simulations, in which an individual has to decide between different practical choices in order to avoid a potential declarative bias (Sörqvist et al., 2013).

What are the usual factors that explain WTP for the environment in the literature?

Personal concern – In a meta-analysis of 46 articles between 1995 and 2006, Bamberg and Möser (2007) emphasize the role of personal concern, i.e., the awareness and knowledge about environmental problems. In their study, problem awareness (as they label it) is a founding stone ultimately leading to a pro-environmental behavior.

Country concern – Whether an individual thinks that environment is a problem for her/his country also positively affect WTP. The study of Shao et al. (2018) is based on Chinese data, and they show that individuals' self-rated pollution conditions is an important positive driver of the WTP for the environment. The last two variables build upon the earlier work of Inglehart (1995), which puts forward postmaterialist values: when individuals have fulfilled their primary needs, they expect a better quality of life, including environmental protection.

Age – Younger individuals are found to be more willing to pay for the environment Tianyu and Meng (2020). The article of Dardanoni and Guerriero (2021) restricts to young people aged 8-19 years old, and still finds the same effect. An earlier study of Gelissen (2007) also finds a significant negative relationship, and underlines that it could either come from a life-cycle effect or from a cohort effect (each generation having a different socialization imprint). However, this factor has no significant impact in other studies (Shao et al., 2018).

Gender – Dardanoni and Guerriero (2021) find that young girls are more willing to pay than boys. Arnocky and Stroink (2011) suggest that a greater ability for empathy of women, and also a greater concern for the environment,

could explain this difference. However, Shao et al. (2018) and Tianyu and Meng (2020) do not find significant effects.

Education – The higher the level of education, the higher the willingness to pay for the environment. Using Chinese data, Tianyu and Meng (2020) show that an additional year of education can increase the WTP for the environment by 33% significantly, and it is confirmed in Shao et al. (2018). An earlier study in the case of Sweden (Carlsson and Johansson-Stenman, 2000) also finds a positive relationship.

Income – Income is often shown to positively influence the willingness to pay for environmental protection (Gelissen, 2007; Shao et al., 2018; Breffle et al., 2015). Authors suggest that it can stem from a direct wealth effect, as higher income makes it easier to arbitrage in favor of pro-environmental and more expensive goods, or in favor of taxation. It may also illustrate the hypothesis of Inglehart (1990), which posits that higher individual income can shift values and priorities, from physical sustenance and safety, towards quality of life (including environmental quality). However, income can have more complex effects. First, a stagnation or decrease of the WTP for the environment can be observed for the very top income (Shao et al., 2018). Second, income inequality can influence this relationship, with more unequal countries showing a lower increase in WTP when income rises (Baumgärtner et al., 2017). Still, the overall relationship remains positive.

Political orientation – The environmental programs differ across political parties, and thus the political orientation of an individual is probably related with her/his willingness to pay for the environment. Dupont and Bateman (2012) show, with data on the United Kingdom, that left- and green voters have relatively higher WTP for collective solutions (improving the water supply infrastructure), whereas right-wing voters have a higher WTP when it comes to private solutions (water softeners at home). The international study of Davidovic et al. (2020) confirms that left-wing individuals have more WTP taxes for the environment (although it depends on the quality of the local government), as did the earlier studies of Neumayer (2004) and Witzke and Urfei (2001), even controlling for income and education.

Religion – An international study on 91 countries using several religious engagement indicators shows a positive association between religion and WTP for the environment (Zemo and Nigus, 2021). However, the relationship may depend with the indicator in question. Peifer et al. (2016), using US data, shows that religious attendance and religious identity are positively related with green consumption, whereas beliefs in an involved God and biblical literalism are negatively related. The study of Dilmaghani (2018) on Canadian data also finds mixed effects. "Unchurched believers" are the most likely to give money to environmental causes, followed by the "strictly secular", and the "very religious" are the least likely to give.

Residence – The literature shows mixed results. In Sweden, the geographical proximity with a natural area can have a positive impact on their willingness to pay for it (Ezebilo et al., 2013), but living in big cities increases the WTP for the environment (Carlsson and Johansson-Stenman, 2000). Besides, An et al. (2024) shows, on Chinese data, that being a farmer has a dampening effect on WTP for the environment. Finally, Tianyu and Meng (2020) finds no significant effect.

Partner – Although the literature focusing precisely on this variable is scarce, one study concludes that partnered individuals have a higher WTP for the environment (Ligus, 2018) whereas other find no significant effect (Joung et al., 2014), or an effect when combined with other variables: being married increases the WTP for urban households, but not rural ones (Tianyu and Meng, 2020).

Child – Having one or more children can drive an individual to be more prone to pay for the environment. It is confirmed in the studies of Carlsson and Johansson-Stenman (2000) and Joung et al. (2014).

We now turn to the literature about our interest variables. We survey the possible impact of, first, social status, and second, prosocial orientation, on the WTP for the environment.

Social status – In our study, we define social status as an individual’s subjective assessment of their relative position in society. These status are thus the expression of individual’s beliefs about their own position, but also about those of others (Mattan et al., 2017). More precisely, when using a ten-point scale ranging from the lowest (1) to the highest (10), social status corresponds to the rung of the scale that respondents assign to themselves within their society.

Several articles address topics closely related to our research question. For example, Sexton and Sexton (2014) demonstrate that the motivation to signal environmentally friendly behavior plays a central role in green consumption choices. In this sense, the willingness to pay for a “green signal” can be interpreted as a willingness to signal one’s social status. More specifically, they show that a non-negligible share of the purchase price of a Toyota Prius can be attributed to this signalling effect, which the authors label as a form of conspicuous conservation (see also Delgado et al., 2015). This mechanism is consistent with the broader theory of conspicuous consumption described by Veblen (1899).

In a pioneering contribution, Griskevicius et al. (2010) report three experimental studies demonstrating the role of social status and prestige motives in the consumption of green products. For instance, participants who were first exposed to narratives describing a favorable social status—without any reference to pro-environmental or cooperative behavior—were subsequently more likely to choose “green” rather than “luxurious” models of a given product (e.g. vacuum cleaner, car). Furthermore, green consumption is associated with being perceived as “nicer”, “caring”, and “altruistic”, i.e. more prosocial.

Chen (2023) synthesizes several studies on the relationship between social class and pro-environmental engagement. They focus on what they term *subjective social class* (corresponding to social status according to our definition) while controlling for *objective social class* (education and income). Their results indicate that middle-class individuals are more likely to engage in pro-environmental actions. This finding is explained by the middle-status anxiety hypothesis: “middle-class individuals tend to feel more insecure and concerned about their social standing compared to individuals at the top or bottom of the social hierarchy (...). As a result, individuals from the middle class may be more inclined to adopt socially desirable behaviors to enhance their social

standing” (Chen, 2023, p. 2). Importantly, this hypothesis does not primarily relate to income. Rather, it provides a socio-psychological foundation for why subjective social status could shape willingness to pay for environmental goods.

Along similar lines, Yan et al. (2021) confirm a stronger propensity of the middle classes to engage in green consumption. They argue that the middle classes simultaneously seek to distinguish themselves from lower classes (need for distinction) while assimilating to upper classes (need for assimilation). By contrast, the drivers of green consumption are weaker for other groups, since lower classes are predominantly motivated by assimilation, and upper classes mainly by distinction. In this respect, the article echoes the theses of sociologist P. Bourdieu on this issue (Bourdieu, 1984). Overall, this study highlights that subjective socioeconomic status strongly influences green consumption. Interestingly, individuals’ perceptions of social inequality (power distance belief) also moderate their willingness to consume green products. The more an individual from an extreme social class (either lower or upper) holds egalitarian views and considers inequalities unjust, the greater their propensity to consume green products, thus approaching the behavior of middle-class consumers.

In turn, Zhong (2024) confirms a strictly increasing relationship: individuals with higher subjective socioeconomic status consume more green products and are willing to donate larger amounts for environmental causes (e.g., to WWF), holding family income, education, and occupation constant. The authors demonstrate the role of two psychological factors in this mechanism. The *sense of control* is an index constructed from survey items measuring the extent to which individuals perceive themselves as capable of influencing life events and relatively free from external constraints (e.g., Lachman and Weaver, 1998). The *life history strategy scale* is an index based on the Mini-K questionnaire, which captures the extent to which individuals follow a “fast” versus a “slow” life strategy. Higher scores indicate a stronger orientation toward long-term planning and delayed rewards (slow strategy), whereas lower scores reflect a preference for immediate benefits and short-term gains (fast strategy) (e.g., Figueredo et al., 2006; Griskevicius et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2017). In short, independently of income level, individuals with low subjective social status report a diminished sense of control and a short-term horizon, reducing their propensity to engage in green consumption. Conversely, individuals with high subjective social status exhibit pro-environmental behavior explained by stronger perceived control and a long-term orientation.

Finally, Gladstone and Bellezza (2024) clearly differentiate objective and subjective social status, and find that green consumption increases monotonically with subjective status. The relationship is quadratic, with consumption rising sharply at high levels of subjective status. Controlling carefully for income, they show for example that green consumption correlates with “green attitudes”, an indicator of environmental concerns and lifestyles. The relationship also holds for less financially demanding behaviors, such as recycling or using reusable bags.

Prosocial orientation – In the context of this article, “prosocial orientation” refers to a preference for acting in favor of the environment *per se*, independently of whether others do so. Based on the survey item “There is no

point in doing what I can for the environment unless others do the same”, we define prosocial orientation as responses of “Strongly disagree” or “Disagree.” Prosocial *orientation* is thus a preference and a psychological disposition, and must be differentiated from willingness to pay. WTP refers to an outcome or an action chosen, and is therefore sometimes described in the literature as a prosocial “choice,” “attitude,” or “behavior.”

Several articles by Benabou and Tirole (Bénabou and Tirole, 2003, 2006, 2025) provide microeconomic foundations for “prosocial orientation” behaviors. The concept of intrinsic motivation that they develop increases an agent’s utility and, in our context, relates to the degree of pro-environmental orientation of the individual³. In their article, all agents are affected by an externality (in our case, an environmental one), but only some individuals have the psychological preference towards a prosocial orientation –either because of the pure moral satisfaction derived from acting (“warm glow”), or because they care about the consequences of their own action (“consequentialism”). The interesting point is that this holds even when the population is large and the individual’s marginal impact on the externality is negligible. In such cases, prosocial orientation reflects an individual inclination to “do one’s part,” even when others do not and when the personal impact is recognized as small. It may correspond to a Kantian desire to act as one would “will” that everyone should act. Conversely, a less prosocially-oriented agent is not sensitive enough to such intrinsic motivation, the satisfaction provided does not meet up with the time and effort spent. However, this agent is still affected by the externality as a whole—that is, the agent benefits from others being willing to act.

Besides intrinsic motivation, reputation or esteem can also drive prosocial orientation to impact willingness to pay. As Bénabou and Tirole (2025) posit, esteem may stem either from social image (the judgment of others) or from self-image. In both cases, the individual is evaluated based on his or her own conduct, that is, on the level of pro-environmental actions. In an experimental framework, Tavoni et al. (2011) study a public goods game grounded in the “tragedy of the commons.” This setting is well suited to environmental issues, as pro-environmental actions entail short-term private costs but only uncertain, long-term collective benefits. They show that, when contributions are anonymous, the participation rate in the collective goal is low; however, when contributions are publicly observable, participation increases significantly. This illustrates how reputation interacts with prosocial orientation, and explains why an individual can be willing to pay even if others are not.

Schumacher (2015) uses the same ISSP database as we do to examine how prosocial orientation –labeled “atomism” in that context– relates to willingness to pay. Although the approach differs, the main finding is consistent with ours: more pessimistic beliefs are associated with a lower willingness to contribute. Our contribution, however, is not merely to rely on a more recent ISSP wave. First, Schumacher (2015) operationalizes constructs through principal

³We refer in particular to their discussion of equation (1) in Bénabou and Tirole (2025). To match their presentation, our *prosocial orientation* variable equals 1 when their intrinsic motivation parameter v is high, and 0 when v is low. By contrast, willingness to pay relates to variable a , which represents the level of prosocial action chosen by the individual.

component analysis; in that specification, “atomism” is only one component of a broader “beliefs” factor; second, willingness to pay is subsumed under a wider “willingness to contribute” factor. While this aggregation offers a useful synoptic view, we argue that the “prosocial orientation” item warrants stand-alone analysis. We therefore study its direct relationship with willingness to pay, providing results that are interpretable at the survey item level and comparable across settings. In doing so, we concur with Schumacher (2015) on the central role of how individuals value their own actions.

In Doran et al. (2015), the perceived direct impact on environmental outcomes is referred to as “self-efficacy.” It is measured with several survey items whose responses are synthesized into a factor via principal components analysis (PCA), aiming to capture one’s perceived ability to make a difference. As such, it is closely aligned with our “prosocial orientation”. Although developed in a tourism context, their approach generalizes to studies of pro-environmental behavior more broadly. They also construct a “collective efficacy” factor that summarizes items about the perceived ability of tourists to solve environmental problems collectively, and a “social comparison” factor that measures how individuals compare their own attitudes with those of others. Their main result is that “self-efficacy” and “collective efficacy” significantly increase willingness to pay for environmental protection, whereas “social comparison” does not. In other words, tourists are prepared to act even if others do not (self-efficacy), and the extent to which they believe others hold similar attitudes (social comparison) does not influence willingness to pay. Moreover, recognizing the importance of coordinated collective action (collective efficacy) is not antithetical to this individual inclination.

This line of inquiry is extended in Doran and Hanss (2022). The authors highlight the role of expectations about others’ cooperation in the willingness to sacrifice personal interests, and show that this effect is mediated by collective and self-efficacy. Put differently, believing in the efficacy of acting independently of what others do can foster pro-environmental behavior even when individuals doubt that others will cooperate. This further supports the importance of measuring prosocial orientation as a key determinant of willingness to pay for environmental protection.

Finally, this review of the literature supports our decision to examine the role of social status and prosocial orientation in individuals’ willingness to pay for environmental protection, and leads us to expect a positive relationship with WTP.

3 Data and Model

3.1 Data description

This section is dedicated to present the data base and the methodology applied in this article. We use data from the fourth International Social Survey Program module about environment, published in 2023 (ISSP, 2023). It is the most recent wave on this topic, the survey includes 44,100 valid responses for 28 countries, ranging from 993 respondents from New Zealand to 4,280 from

Switzerland⁴. The survey is composed of sixty questions about environment and as many on individual characteristics and demographic information. In this edition, responses were collected between October 2019 (for Hungary) and August 2023 (for Denmark), but mainly at the end of 2020 and during 2021.

As we aim to study willingness to pay (WTP) in all its forms, we use the answers to three directly related questions. The twelfth question is: "How willing would you be to pay much higher prices in order to protect the environment?" and is used as a baseline. This question is rephrased as "how willing would you be to pay much higher taxes in order to protect the environment?" and "how willing would you be to accept cuts in your standard of living in order to protect the environment?" for the thirteenth and fourteenth questions, respectively.

Using these variables, we focus on a purely qualitative willingness to pay (WTP) to protect the environment in general. The aim, therefore, is not to estimate how much individuals are willing to pay, but rather to identify factors likely to influence the general trend. Similarly, although the current context lends itself to studying climate change, this is not the question directly posed here.

The answers to these questions are measured on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "1 - Very willing" to "5 - Very unwilling." We reverse the order of responses to simplify interpretation: in our model, a response of 4 or 5 for these three questions indicates a positive willingness to pay to protect the environment. In other words, 1 corresponds to being "very unwilling", while 5 corresponds to being "very willing" to pay more to protect the environment.

These three questions all have a valid response rate of approximately 97%. However as we can see in Figure 1, the question about taxes is the only one whose mode is not equal to 4, but rather 2. In our sample, most respondents are unwilling to pay higher taxes to protect the environment. We obtain similar results in terms of the computed mean. The average response for the willingness to pay higher taxes question is the lowest, with a mean of 2.57, while the other two are above 2.9.⁵ This reflects a preference for participating in the environmental transition oneself rather than involving the state and potential intermediaries through taxes.

⁴The countries in the base are : Austria, Australia, Switzerland, China, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, France, Croatia, Hungary, Iceland, India, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Lithuania, Norway, New Zealand, Philippines, Russia Federation, Sweden, Slovakia, Slovenia, Thailand, Taiwan, United States, South Africa.

⁵A possible reason for this under-representation of the "Very willing" response is the question format. Indeed, the wording "much higher prices/taxes" may lead to self-restraint on the part of lower-income individuals, who may feel unable to contribute despite wanting to.

Figure 1: *Source: Authors' calculations based on the ISSP Environment IV module. Responses range from "1- Very unwilling" to "5- Very willing". There are 12,946 individuals who are willing to pay much higher prices to protect the environment.*

The first explanatory variable is the perceived social status in society. The twenty-fourth demographic question (named TOPBOT) is "In our society, there are groups which tend to be towards the top and groups which tend to be towards the bottom. Where would you put yourself on this scale?". Respondents have to choose their position in a 10-point scale from 1-the lowest to 10-the top. Consistent with the sociological literature, there is an over-representation of the middle bracket (5-6) with 43.75% of the sample (Phan, 2011) as we can see in the left part of Figure 2. This question allows variety in respondent's opinions of themselves and the rest of society.

To lighten the regression and improve the population in each class, we have chosen to aggregate the responses. In our baseline model, our social status variable (SocStatus) is divided into 3 classes: "1- Low social status" made up of answers 1 to 4, "2- Median social status" made up of answers 5 and 6, and finally, "3- High social status" made up of answers 7 to 10. In addition, to supplement this initial simplified version, we also use another classification of the Social Status variable. To test robustness, we create a second, less aggregated variable with five categories consisting of two responses each: 1-2, 3-4, 5-6, 7-8, and 9-10. The main results using this variable are in 5.2

The second explanatory variable is the attitude towards the behavior of other individuals, the prosocial orientation.⁶ Since the transformation must be global, individual actions may seem derisory and therefore pointless. The question 12d can be a proxy of this belief : "How much do you agree or disagree with :[...] There is no point in doing what I can for the environment unless others do the same." The response has the form of a 5-propositions Likert scale from "1-Agree strongly" to "5-Disagree strongly". 20,497

⁶Here we make a distinction between the prosocial action represented by WTP and prosocial orientation as explain before.

individuals disagree or strongly disagree with this statement. So in the right part of Figure 2, 50.63% of our overall sample believes that individuals should not wait for others to act before taking action themselves. On the other hand, the other half of our sample believe that there is no point in making an effort if it is not followed up by the rest of society. To facilitate model interpretations, we aggregate the variable into a dummy. We aggregate the individuals who answered “Disagree” or “Strongly disagree” into a binary variable entitled “Prosocial Oriented”, in this case worth 1.

Figure 2: Authors’ calculations based on the ISSP Environment IV module. For Social Status, responses range from “1- The bottom” to “10- The top”. For Prosocial Orientation, they range from “1- Strongly agree” to “5- Strongly disagree”. There are 10,081 individuals with a social status of 5 and 8,072 with a social status of 6. These 18,153 individuals are grouped in the middle category (second out of 3) of our aggregate variable of social status.

In line with the literature, we create a list of control variables which can have a direct impact on the individual’s willingness to pay. We only use responses from the ISSP IV Environment module survey.

Firstly, we create two variables that can be linked to the notion of environmental concerns. We create our first indicator of personal concern based on the sixth question “how concerned are you about environmental issues?”. The response here is a 5-proposition Likert scale ranging from “1-Not at all concerned” to “5-Very concerned”. We create a dummy variable taking 1 if the answer is either 4 or 5, the respondent is either concerned or very concerned about environmental issues. We obtain 27,142 individuals that are personally concerned, i.e. 65,14% of the sample. Only two countries, South Africa and Thailand, have less than half of their respondent feeling concerned about the environment while more than 80% of the Slovenian respondents do. We consider this variable to be an indicator of personal concern, and believe that it will be closely correlated with its willingness to pay.

To complete this first variable, we create a second indicator of “Country concern” based on the first two questions of the ISSP questionnaire : “Which of these issues is the most important for [Country] today?” and “Next most important issue for [Country] today?”. The list of possible responses is Health care, Education, Crime, *The environment*, Immigration, The economy, Terrorism and Poverty. Our dummy variable is set to 1 if the individual chooses “The environment” for one of these two questions. 9,496 respondents,

i.e. 22.79% of our total sample, consider "the environment" to be one of their country's main problems. There are major differences within our sample : in Australia, Germany, Norway, and Switzerland, more than 40% of the population considers the environment to be one of the national main issues, while in Croatia, Hungary, Philippine, Russia, Slovenia, South Africa, and Thailand, it's less than 10%.

The Age variable is kept as given by the respondents. The youngest has 15 years old and the oldest 103. Our sample has a mean of 50.54 years old and a median of 51.⁷

The Gender is a binary variable with 0 if male and 1 if female, there are 22,270 females in our sample, i.e. 53.54%.

The Education is derived from the EDULEVEL question and is set as a discrete ordinal variable: 1 if the individuals have stopped before or at upper secondary education, 2 if they have short-cycle tertiary education and 3 if they have validated more than a lower tertiary diploma. 57.23% of our sample stopped before completing high school, 30.11% have completed a degree equivalent to three years after the secondary diploma or less and finally 12.66% validated long-cycle education. The only country where the mean and the median are above 2, meaning that half of their sample has completed more than secondary education, is Russia.

As we saw in the literature review, income is often cited as one of the main determinants of willingness to pay for environmental protection. In the ISSP survey, there are two questions about income : one asking the personal income ([Country].INC variables) and the second one for household income ([Country].RINC variables). These two incomes have a correlation of approximately 0.6, except for China, which is 0.02. We transform the household income variables into a more aggregated indicator (Income). We chose this household income variable because it avoids over-representation of individuals with an income of 0. Since these questions are asked in different ways, annual, monthly or weekly income, we create an relative income variable for our sample.

To do this, we calculate the quintile thresholds within each country and classify individuals accordingly. The appendix table A.1 shows the different quintile. This reclassification as discrete factor gives us 5 categories ranging from 5,758 individuals (below the 1st quintile) to 7,497 individuals (above the last quintile). By definition, the highest class is the one with the largest number of respondents. In our opinion, this does not significantly alter the results obtained. This modification allows us to facilitate the interpretation of our coefficients and to disaggregate the potential non-linear effect of income. We apply a second transformation to this variable to enable comparison with the social status. We thus create a variable in 3 categories: individuals with an income less than or equal to 40% of the national population, those between 40 and 60% and individuals earning more than 60% of their compatriots. The first class includes 11,552 individuals, i.e. 36.21% of the sample. The median class includes 6,210 individuals, i.e. 19.46% and the upper class

⁷In the literature, some authors take the log of the age or cut the distribution in some classes. We test these two alternative methods but this doesn't change our results so we keep the variable as it is.

14,145 respondents, i.e. 44.33%. For this study, the income question is the least answered by individuals, with 23,42% of missing values.

The political orientation is also represented in this survey (PARTY_LR question) so we decompose it in three dummy variables : Left, Center and Right. We keep the category Center to consider the central block, even if studies often use only the left/right dichotomy. We aggregate here far-left and far-right in their respective sides because of their ideological proximity about environment. In our sample, there are respectively 18.9% of our sample that are left-wing, 13.95% for center and 19.15% right-wing.⁸ The sum of these three questions corresponds to almost 50% of our sample, which limits the risk of multicollinearity that could arise. The remainder is made up of no answer to the survey question, “other” or “Invalid Ballot”. Unfortunately, these answers do not allow us to consider the specific case of abstainers.

The individual’s religion can also have impacts on their willingness to pay when it concerns the environment. Since we cannot study their practices, we rely on the religion to which respondents declare they belong (nationally specific questions aggregated in RELIGGRP question). One third of the sample, 14,807 individuals, considers themselves belong to one of the proposed religion.

Within the literature, the geographical proximity with a natural area can have an impact on the willingness to protect it. To take this potential channel into account, we use the answers to the question: “Would you describe the place where you live as ...” (URBRURAL in the survey). The possibilities are: “1- A big city”, “2- The suburbs or outskirts of a big city”, “3- A town or a small city”, “4- A country village” or “5- A farm or home in the country”. We create a dummy called “Bigcity” corresponding to aggregated responses 1 and 2, representing 15,799 individuals, i.e. 41.37% of the sample.

The individual’s family situation can also influence his or her willingness to pay for the environment. The question PARTLIV asks whether the respondent has “a spouse or a steady partner”. We create a dummy for the 27,521 individuals, i.e. 70.23% of the sample, that have a partner.

In the same way, we create a last dummy for the presence of children in the household. We use two questions (HHCHILDR and HHTODD) to create a binary variable, set to 1 if the household includes at least one minor child. We have 11,138 respondents, i.e. 30.98% living with minors in the same household.

3.2 Model

In the case of discrete dependent variable, we set up a ordered logistic model consistent with the literature in this topic (Shao et al., 2018) and based on Wooldridge (2010).

$$WTP_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 SocStatus_i + \alpha_2 ProsocOrientation_i + \alpha_i X_i + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

With i represents the respondent, α are parameters to be estimate and ϵ_i the residual term. X_i corresponds to a vector of control variables including :

⁸China and Taiwan are not represented in one of these categories as their responses are not available in the survey.

national concern, personal concern, age, gender, education, income, political orientation, religion, household location, family status and country dummies.

The ordered logit model of the willingness to pay (WTP) can be found by using a latent variable model, which corresponds to a linear function of the explanatory variables. This second model depends on four cut points γ^9 to divide the 5 categories of the latent explained variable :

$$\begin{aligned}
WTP &= 1 && \text{if } WTP_{latent} \leq \gamma_1 \\
WTP &= 2 && \text{if } \gamma_1 < WTP_{latent} \leq \gamma_2 \\
WTP &= 3 && \text{if } \gamma_2 < WTP_{latent} \leq \gamma_3 \\
WTP &= 4 && \text{if } \gamma_3 < WTP_{latent} \leq \gamma_4 \\
WTP &= 5 && \text{if } WTP_{latent} > \gamma_4
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

With this configuration, we can calculate the probability that individual i belongs to class k of our WTP variable using the distribution function :

$$\pi_{ik} = P(WTP_i = k | x'_i) = P(\gamma_{k-1} < \alpha' x'_i + \epsilon_i \leq \gamma_k) = \Lambda(\gamma_k - \alpha' x'_i) - \Lambda(\gamma_{k-1} - \alpha' x'_i) \tag{3}$$

Where x'_i represents the explanatory variables, α' the estimated coefficients in Equation 1 and Λ the distribution function of a logistic function.

However, the ordered logit stands on a main hypothesis : the parallel regression assumption (also known as proportional odds assumption). This means that the coefficients α' estimated in the model cannot change according to the class k of our explained variable. Because in our case the data allow us to reject this hypothesis, at least for some variables, we use the Partial Proportional Odds Model (PPOM) developed by Peterson and Harrell (1990). Using their methodology, we test for each independent variables whether it rejects this assumption using a Brant test with a 95% level of confidence. Then, we remove the proportionality constraint on the specific coefficients, which give us :

$$\pi_{ik} = P(WTP_i = k | x'_i) = P(\gamma_{k-1} < \alpha'_k x'_i + \epsilon_i \leq \gamma_k) \tag{4}$$

where α'_k is the vector of coefficients, which may vary according to WTP classes.

To analyze the sign or significance of the impact of our variables, we can use the coefficients given by the model. But to estimate the range of this effect, we compute the marginal effects of each dependent variables. These marginal effects correspond to the partial derivative of our model for each classes of our dependent variable at one point of our independent variables. These marginal effects give us the probability of belonging to each value of our dependent variable, depending on the differentiation of our explanatory variables. We calculate the change in the probability of belonging in one of

⁹We use 4 cut points because there are 5 categories in the WTP explained variable.

our dependent variable classes when one of our explanatory variables changes from its reference level. For instance, we compute the odds variation of willing to pay when an individual is concerned about environment compared to an identical individual who has no such concerns.

4 Results

In this section, we will present the results of our baseline scenario. As we said, we use a Partial Proportional Odds Model to estimate marginal effects of our independent variables on the willingness to pay much higher prices dependent variable. We perform this analysis via the *gologit2* (Williams, 2006) and the *margins* functions, available on Stata. In this test, we run our logistic model with our explaining and control variables to explain the willingness to pay much higher prices. We also add countries dummies to take into account national specific characteristics. Marginal effects of this model are shown in Table 1.

Each coefficients represent the variation in probabilities of being in each class of our dependent variable according to a different value of the independent variable. This corresponds to a *Ceteris Paribus* reasoning, in which we study the difference in our dependent variable when only one of our independent variables differs from its reference level between two individuals who are otherwise identical.

Our first variable of interest is the effect of perceived social status on willingness to pay much higher prices for the environment. With the reference level set at 2, the marginal effect corresponds to the variation in the probability of being willing or not willing to pay more if the respondent considers him/herself below or above the median class. It corresponds to the feeling of being undervalued or socially valued compared to the median. We can see that feeling socially undervalued increases the probability of being unwilling to pay more to protect the environment by 1.54%, and decreases the probability of being willing to do so by 3.82%. These effects are even more pronounced for extreme responses : it increases the probability to be very unwilling by 6.34% and decreases the odds to be very willing by 7.28%. Conversely, in the third row, we can see the effects of feeling above the median social class. Being at the top of the social hierarchy increases the probability of being willing to pay higher prices by 5.44% and of being very willing by 1.53%. It also decreases the probability to be indifferent by 2.77%, which may reflect greater consideration for environmental quality in general. These results are consistent with the literature and show the role that social status can play in an individual's pro-environmental actions.

Being oriented towards prosocial behaviors reduces the probability of being unwilling to pay much higher prices to protect it by 1.98%. Otherwise, it increases the likelihood of being willing to pay higher prices by 7.69%. On the one hand, this decreases the probability of refusing to pay more, and on the other, increases the probability of being willing to pay more. We can see that, in line with the literature, prosocial orientation has a homo-

Table 1: Marginal effects of social status and of prosocial orientation on WTP much higher prices to protect the environment.

WTP_{price}	1. Very unwilling	2. Unwilling	3. Neutral	4. Willing	5. Very willing
Low social status	0.0634*** (0.009)	0.0154* (0.009)	-0.0333*** (0.006)	-0.0382*** (0.008)	-0.00728* (0.004)
Median social status	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
High social status	-0.0179*** (0.005)	-0.0241*** (0.006)	-0.0277*** (0.006)	0.0544*** (0.007)	0.0153*** (0.006)
Prosocial orientation	-0.0486*** (0.009)	-0.0198*** (0.006)	-0.0314*** (0.006)	0.0769*** (0.01)	0.0230*** (0.004)
Personal concern	-0.0863*** (0.01)	-0.0676*** (0.009)	-0.0236*** (0.007)	0.114*** (0.009)	0.0636*** (0.008)
Country concern	-0.0789*** (0.008)	-0.0430*** (0.008)	-0.00223 (0.008)	0.0825*** (0.007)	0.0416*** (0.005)
Age	0.00007 (0.0002)	0.00005 (0.0002)	-0.00000 (0.00007)	-0.00009 (0.0003)	-0.00003 (0.0001)
Sex	-0.0118** (0.005)	0.0133*** (0.005)	0.00756 (0.006)	-0.00394 (0.006)	-0.00513* (0.003)
Education	-0.0155*** (0.004)	-0.0112** (0.004)	-0.0162*** (0.005)	0.0291*** (0.005)	0.0138*** (0.002)
Income	-0.0175*** (0.005)	-0.00395 (0.003)	-0.00507 (0.003)	0.0264*** (0.003)	0.00010 (0.002)
Left-wing	-0.0400*** (0.007)	-0.0302*** (0.005)	0.00111*** (0.0003)	0.0506*** (0.009)	0.0185*** (0.003)
Center	-0.0422*** (0.01)	-0.0195* (0.01)	-0.00876 (0.008)	0.0604*** (0.01)	0.0100** (0.004)
Right-wing	0.0108 (0.007)	0.00819 (0.006)	-0.00030 (0.0003)	-0.0137 (0.009)	-0.00502 (0.003)
Religious	0.00439 (0.004)	0.00332 (0.003)	-0.00012 (0.0001)	-0.00556 (0.006)	-0.00203 (0.002)
Big city resident	-0.00916* (0.005)	-0.00692* (0.004)	0.00025 (0.0002)	0.0116* (0.007)	0.00424* (0.002)
Partner	0.00441 (0.003)	0.00333 (0.003)	-0.00012 (0.0001)	-0.00557 (0.004)	-0.00204 (0.002)
Child	0.0215*** (0.005)	-0.00006 (0.005)	-0.00166 (0.007)	-0.0174*** (0.006)	-0.00242 (0.004)
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observation	3,915	5,665	6,228	8,403	1,506

N = 25,717. McFadden adjusted $R^2 = 0.4305$. Standard errors in parentheses.

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

An individual who feels they belong to the lowest social classes will be 6.34% more likely to be strongly unwilling to pay much higher prices, compared to an identical individual who considers themselves to be middle class.

geneous and positive effect on the willingness to pay higher prices to protect it.

We can see that feeling like you're part of a disadvantaged social class can lower how much people are willing to pay, and the opposite is true for those who feel like they're part of a privileged social class. So, in addition to the social benefits, improving the perceived situation of individuals can lead to greater consideration for the environment. In the same way, individuals having prosocial orientation tend to be more willing to pay to protect the environment. This may be a sign that certain social policies also have a positive impact on the environment.

Among the control variables, feeling personally concerned about the environment is the main driver of being willing to pay higher prices to protect it. Indeed, it increases the probability to be willing by 11.4% and decreases the probability to be unwilling to pay higher prices by 6.8%. In the same way but with smaller effects, considering the environment as a main issue for the country tends to increase the probability of being willing to pay to protect it. Taking these into account is therefore necessary to include citizens in the environmental transition, given its driving force on their WTP.

Among the control variables found in the literature, not all have an effect on our sample. Aging has no significant effect in this configuration, consistent with the results of Shao et al. (2018). Older individuals do not differ from younger individuals in terms of their WTP level. We have next the effect of being a woman rather than a man. In our sample, there are mixed effects between the sexes in terms of their impact on willingness to pay or not to protect the environment. In one hand, being female increases the probability to be unwilling to pay higher prices by 1.33% and, in the other hand it decreases the probabilities of being at either extreme, either very unwilling or very willing. These mixed results are similar to those reported in the literature. We can see then the link between individual's education and WTP. In line with the literature, a higher level of education increases the probability of being willing to pay more than 2.9% and decreases the probability of being unwilling by 1.1%. We can thus see that education improves environmental awareness and action. Then, income have a positive and homogeneous effect on the WTP. So, a richer individual will have an increase by 2.64% of the probability to be willing to pay much higher prices to protect the environment and a decrease of 1.75% to be very unwilling to do so. We also test a categorical income in order to decompose its effect in cases it is non-linear. The main results are presented in Table 3 in the Robustness section and full results are in Appendix A.3. The next three rows show the effects of political orientation. Being left-wing or centrist has a positive effect on WTP but less significant for the latter. Being right-wing has no significant effect in our sample. That contradicts the findings in the literature on the preference for individual action among right-wing voters. Having religious beliefs has no significant effects on the probability to be willing or not to pay higher prices to protect the environment. A significant variable is the household location. Living in a big city or theirs suburbs tends to increase the probability to be willing to pay higher prices to protect the environment

by 1.16%. In our case, being a city dweller has a marked positive effect on willingness to pay. Finally, the household composition has no impact on the individual's WTP when we look at couples, but has a negative effect when there are minors in the household. For the latter, one reason that may explain this difference with the results highlighted in the literature is the fact that the authors base their findings on a single country (Sweden for Carlsson and Johansson-Stenman (2000) and Korea for Joung et al. (2014)).

Even when these control variables are taken into account, we see that social status and prosocial orientation continue to play an important role in explaining individuals' willingness to pay to protect the environment. Social policies, which are potentially less costly than direct subsidies or structural changes, can influence individuals' perceptions, values, and attitudes toward others, thereby playing a role in environmental transition. In connection with these public policies, one aspect of willingness to pay concerns taxes.

In the ISSP database, responses to the question on WTP more taxes to protect the environment show a different distribution from the baseline model. One possible reason is the introduction of an intermediary into individuals' consumption choices. We can then replicate our model on this other dependent variable to compare effects. Table 2 shows the main results. Appendix A.2 presents all results.

Table 2: Marginal effects of social status and prosocial orientation on WTP higher taxes to protect the environment.

WTP_{taxes}	1. Very unwilling	2. Unwilling	3. Neutral	4. Willing	5. Very willing
Low social status	0.0715*** (0.01)	0.00282 (0.008)	-0.0444*** (0.005)	-0.0269*** (0.009)	-0.00299 (0.004)
Median social status	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
High social status	-0.0205** (0.01)	-0.0127** (0.006)	-0.0236*** (0.007)	0.0456*** (0.008)	0.0112** (0.005)
Prosocial orientation	-0.0563*** (0.01)	-0.00319 (0.008)	-0.0162* (0.008)	0.0653*** (0.01)	0.0104*** (0.003)
Control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	6,124	6,765	5,756	5,865	1,072

N = 25,582. McFadden adjusted $R^2 = 0.4199$. Standard errors in parentheses.

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

An individual who feels they belong to the lowest social classes will be 7.15% more likely to be strongly unwilling to pay much higher taxes, compared to an identical individual who considers themselves to be middle class.

With higher taxes, we can see that the effects of social status change. Feeling in a lower social class has higher effects on being very unwilling to protect the environment through taxes and on being neutral. On the other hand, feeling socially valued has less negative effects on being unwilling, a constant negative effect on being neutral and less positive on being willing. Moreover, being pro-socially oriented tends to increase the probability to be very unwilling but has a positive effect on being neutral to pay higher taxes to protect the environment. To sum up, when we study the willingness to pay taxes, there is a general increase in the number of individuals unwilling to pay more, but the factors mentioned above to explain this are less significant.

These results may show that individuals tend to be more inclined to participate in the transition when it involves higher prices than higher taxes. Using funds to improve the sense of social inclusion would create a positive domino effect for the environment. Encouraging individuals to act on their own, without waiting for others, would reinforce this phenomenon.

5 Robustness tests

In this section, we present the robustness tests we have set up to confirm our results. For the moment, we have only carried out tests on the different variables and their transformation in our model.

5.1 Results with categorical income

In this section, we modify our basic model by treating income as a categorical variable with three classes. Indeed, income is often considered a major determinant of individuals' WTP. As the Income variable (INC) is encoded from 1 to 3, we set the reference level at 2 in order to compare with the median. The results for our dependent variables and income are presented in Table 3. The Appendix A.3 contains the full results.

Table 3: Marginal effects of social status, prosocial orientation and categorical income on WTP higher prices to protect the environment.

WTP_{price}	1. Very unwilling	2. Unwilling	3. Neutral	4. Willing	5. Very willing
Low social status	0.0635*** (0.009)	0.0157* (0.009)	-0.0335*** (0.006)	-0.0388*** (0.008)	-0.00696* (0.004)
Median social status	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
High social status	-0.0176*** (0.005)	-0.0242*** (0.006)	-0.0275*** (0.006)	0.0543*** (0.007)	0.0150*** (0.006)
Prosocial orientation	-0.0487*** (0.009)	-0.0198*** (0.006)	-0.0315*** (0.006)	0.0771*** (0.01)	0.0229*** (0.004)
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Low Income	0.00896** (0.004)	0.00608** (0.002)	-0.000648** (0.0003)	-0.0105** (0.004)	-0.00390** (0.002)
Median Income	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
High Income	-0.0263*** (0.007)	-0.000889 (0.005)	-0.00968* (0.005)	0.0383*** (0.005)	-0.00140 (0.003)
Control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observation	3,915	5,665	6,228	8,403	1,506

N = 25,717. McFadden adjusted $R^2 = 0.4305$. Standard errors in parentheses.

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

An individual who feels they belong to the lowest social classes will be 6.35% more likely to be strongly unwilling to pay much higher prices, compared to an identical individual who considers themselves to be middle class.

We can see that the coefficients of our dependent variables remain close to the baseline scenario. This is even more remarkable given that the Social Status variable remains significant, with strong coefficients. We can therefore say that, for our sample, the effect of social status is not directly linked to the effect of household financial resources, even if we take into account non-linear effect of income variable.

5.2 Results with less aggregated Social Status

Since responses to the social status question are on a scale of 1 to 10, we tested our variable with a lower level of aggregation. This allows us to decompose the effects present in the basic model. Rather than grouping them into 3 classes, we use 5 classes here.¹⁰ The third level is set as a reference to maintain a comparison with the median. Table 4 presents the main results. Appendix A.4 shows all results.

Table 4: Marginal effects estimates with less aggregated Social Status variable.

WTP_{price}	1. Very unwilling	2. Unwilling	3. Neutral	4. Willing	5. Very willing
Bottom Social Status	0.110*** (0.01)	0.0132 (0.01)	-0.0640*** (0.01)	-0.0630*** (0.008)	0.00381 (0.009)
Low Social Status	0.0495*** (0.009)	0.0169* (0.009)	-0.0241*** (0.007)	-0.0310*** (0.009)	-0.0113*** (0.003)
Median social status	Reference level				
High Social Status	-0.0227*** (0.005)	-0.0189*** (0.007)	-0.0232*** (0.006)	0.0529*** (0.007)	0.0118* (0.006)
Top Social Status	0.0120 (0.01)	-0.0639*** (0.01)	-0.0590*** (0.01)	0.0732*** (0.02)	0.0377*** (0.007)
Prosocial orientation	-0.0483*** (0.009)	-0.0199*** (0.006)	-0.0324*** (0.005)	0.0776*** (0.011)	0.0230*** (0.004)
Control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observation	3,915	5,665	6,228	8,403	1,506

N = 25,717. McFadden adjusted $R^2 = 0.4312$. Standard errors in parentheses.

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

An individual who feels they belong to the lowest social classes will be 11% more likely to be strongly unwilling to pay much higher prices, compared to an identical individual who considers themselves to be middle class.

We can see that the results are still homogeneous and consistent with the baseline scenario. Therefore, the results are pulled by the center of the distribution (Low and High social status) rather than the extremes, especially the bottom one, whose effects are less significant but with strong adherence to the "Very unwilling" case. Feeling above the rest of the population strongly increases the likelihood of willing to pay more for the environment and decreases the unwillingness to pay for it.

5.3 Results for willingness to pay by cutting standards of living

In this model, we seek to explain the latest formulation of WTP proposed by the ISSP: cutting in the standards of living to protect the environment. As presented above, the responses to this third formulation are similar to those to the question about paying higher prices. Table 5 presents the main results. Appendix A.5 shows all results.

With this latest WTP measure, social status has less effects than in the baseline. This is a rather surprising result given its initial importance. Whether individual's social status is lower or higher than the median, the coefficients are almost twice as low and less significant than in the baseline scenario. Conversely, adopting a proactive behavior has a major effect: being proactive

¹⁰The 5 new classes are respectively composed of answers : 1-2, 3-4, 5-6, 7-8, 9-10.

Table 5: Marginal effects of all variables on willingness to pay by cutting in living standards.

$WTP_{Living\ Standards}$	1. Very unwilling	2. Unwilling	3. Neutral	4. Willing	5. Very willing
Low social status	0.0464*** (0.007)	0.0133 (0.008)	-0.0377*** (0.006)	-0.0237*** (0.009)	0.00155 (0.004)
Median social status	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
High social status	0.00193 (0.007)	-0.00108 (0.008)	-0.0224*** (0.006)	0.00516 (0.008)	0.0164*** (0.005)
Prosocial orientation	-0.0524*** (0.01)	-0.0275*** (0.008)	-0.0320*** (0.007)	0.0844*** (0.01)	0.0275*** (0.005)
Control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	3,872	5,606	6,141	8,344	1,492

N = 25,455. Standard errors in parentheses.

***, **, and * represent significances at 1%, 5%, and 10%. McFadden adjusted $R^2 = 0.4290$.

An individual who feels they belong to the lowest social classes will be 4.64% more likely to be strongly unwilling to cut in their standard of living, compared to an identical individual who considers themselves to be middle class.

increases by more than 8% the probability to be willing to cut in the standards of living to protect the environment. These results tend to highlight the importance of social preferences when we study the WTP for the environment.

5.4 Subjective or objective social status ?

Based on the ISSP responses available to us, we created a variable representing the respondent’s subjective social status. However, in sociological and behavioral literature, social status is a construct based primarily on education and income (Chen, 2023). In line with the literature, we create a new variable to determine whether these preliminary results stem from objective social status or a more subjective status. To do this, we used a reduced version of the PPOM regression to explain the link between our social status variable (Social Status mentioned above) and two explanatory variables: income and education.

$$SocialStatus_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Education_i + \alpha_2 Income_i + \epsilon_i \quad (5)$$

In this regression, Education and Income are both considered as categorical variables in order to improve prediction. We then use the results of this model to predict which social category an individual should fall into based on their objective characteristics. The difference between this “objective” social status and the responses to the ISSP questionnaire therefore corresponds to the subjective part of social status: their beliefs. These beliefs are classified in the same way as initial social status: 5 quintiles then aggregated into the lowest 40%, median 20%, and highest 40%. A negative belief corresponds to individuals who undervalue their social status. A positive belief corresponds to individuals who overvalue themselves. We then integrate this new variable into our initial regression in order to test whether the results found to explain willingness to pay stem from the “belief” component or not.

We can see in Table 6 that the results are identical to those of our baseline. Full results are presented in Appendix A.6. Thus, we can say that subjective

social status has a significant link with WTP for the environment. We still have the same effect of individuals that undervalued themselves : in one hand it increases their probability to be unwilling to pay higher prices and in the other hand, it decreases the probability to be willing.

Table 6: Marginal effects of beliefs about social status and proactive behavior on WTP higher prices to protect the environment.

WTP_{prices}	1. Very unwilling	2. Unwilling	3. Neutral	4. Willing	5. Very willing
Lowest beliefs	0.0378*** (0.007)	0.0145** (0.006)	-0.0309*** (0.007)	-0.0152** (0.006)	-0.00619 (0.004)
Median beliefs	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
Highest beliefs	-0.0174*** (0.004)	-0.0164*** (0.006)	-0.0348*** (0.009)	0.0534*** (0.007)	0.0151*** (0.005)
Prosocial orientation	-0.0492*** (0.009)	-0.0197*** (0.006)	-0.0319*** (0.005)	0.0774*** (0.01)	0.0234*** (0.004)
Control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	3,915	5,665	6,228	8,403	1,506

N = 25,717. McFadden adjusted $R^2 = 0.4299$. Standard errors in parentheses.

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

An individual who has a low belief, i.e. who undervalued themselves, will be 3.78% more likely to be strongly unwilling to pay much higher prices, compared to an identical individual who considers themselves accurately.

6 Discussion and Conclusion

We are aware of limits and possible extensions to this study and we present some here. Being based on a single survey facilitates model operation, thanks to the homogeneity of our variables, but limits the generalization we can make of the results. Extend the database to include more diversified sources, especially temporally, can help us to take into account changes that may occur or structural differences. These extensions should take into account the national context and the level of awareness of the climate crisis. Moreover, we have limited ourselves to the use of a ordered logistic model, but there are others that are relevant in our case, like probit if we transform our WTP variables into dummies.

To conclude, based on the 2020 wave of the ISSP environment module, we show that there are links between individuals' social status and wheter they are prosocially oriented and their willingness to pay to protect the environment. We used a Partial Proportional Odds Model to estimate the odds' variation to be willing to pay more to protect the environment. To our knowledge, perceived social status has never been shown to have an impact on WTP. This study completes this gap by showing a strongly positive effect on WTP to protect the environment of feeling more valued, and thus a real need for inclusive social policies. Improving people's social situation would also have a positive impact on their willingness to take action to protect the environment. Furthermore, adopting a prosocial behavior means greater willingness to pay higher prices to protect the environment.

These findings can be used to show the importance of people's opinions in

encouraging transition. Political or individual actions taken in this direction must be as fair as possible to encourage others to do the same and thus improve participation and involvement. This shows the complementarity between individual views and political actions because both are needed to accomplish the transition.

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A Appendix

A.1 Relative income variable

In Table A.1, we present the details of the construction of our income variable based on the ISSP household income responses. In the dataset, income can either be monthly or weekly so we annualized. To facilitate comparison, we present annual income express in PPP here. However, to compute our variable, we use the initial income variable given in the ISSP dataset.

For Denmark, the stated income corresponds to annually and not monthly income in the ISSP dataset. For Croatia, the local currency is currently the euro (EUR), since January 2023. However, Croatian data was collected in June and July 2021, and the conversion factor Kuna (HRK) - International dollar (Int\$) provided by the IMF corresponds more to a Croatian euro - Int\$ exchange rate. To calculate the Croatia line, we therefore applied the exchange rate of 7.5345 HRK for 1 EUR (provided by the ECB) to the ISSP's annual income and then the PPP conversion factor.

Table A.1: Annualized income variable thresholds to create quintiles.

Country	Implied PPP rate	First thresh-old	Second	Third	Fourth thresh-old
Austria	0.698	28 367	34 384	48 138	64 470
Australia	1.432	25 862	43 575	72 626	108 939
Switzerland	1.007	57 200	82 820	97 120	134 062
China	3.796	5 269	10 537	18 967	31 612
Germany	0.697	32 281	45 194	64 562	81 779
Denmark	6.423	54 492	70 061	116 768	163 475
Spain	0.578	28 028	36 332	60 208	74 740
Finland	0.776	35 728	58 763	81 959	111 155
France	0.659	30 118	43 703	60 783	87 405
Croatia	0.411	23 251	34 876	46 501	58 127
Hungary	156.818	10 330	15 304	20 661	30 609
Iceland	144.198	45 770	70 736	99 863	133 150
Italy	0.596	26 678	37 752	55 369	65 436
Japan	92.505	27 026	48 646	59 456	91 887
South Korea	786.305	30 523	45 784	68 676	96 146
Lithuania	0.471	14 268	24 713	35 669	50 955
Norway	10.745	47 883	72 359	98 278	113 448
New Zealand	1.443	25 988	45 045	86 625	103 950
Philippines	19.082	2 515	4 402	6 289	12 577
Russia	26.133	9 184	13 776	18 368	27 551
Sweden	8.227	36 465	55 427	80 224	109 396
Slovenia	0.530	20 377	33 962	45 283	67 925
Thailand	10.888	7 715	13 226	22 043	44 085
Taiwan	13.719	21 867	39 361	65 602	91 843
United States	1.000	27 500	55 000	82 500	120 000
South Africa	7.247	1 449	2 898	6 623	20 698

All variables come from IV wave of the ISSP Environment Module (ISSP, 2023). Annualized household income expressed in Implied PPP provided by the International Monetary Fund (IMF).

A.2 Marginal effects of WTP higher taxes

Table A.2 presents all marginal effects of our model on being willing or not to pay much higher taxes to protect the environment.

Table A.2: Marginal effects of social status and proactive behavior on WTP higher taxes to protect the environment.

WTP_{taxes}	1. Very unwilling	2. Unwilling	3. Neutral	4. Willing	5. Very willing
Low social status	0.0715*** (0.01)	0.00282 (0.008)	-0.0444*** (0.005)	-0.0269*** (0.009)	-0.00299 (0.004)
Median social status	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
High social status	-0.0205** (0.01)	-0.0127** (0.006)	-0.0236*** (0.007)	0.0456*** (0.008)	0.0112** (0.005)
Prosocial orientation	-0.0563*** (0.01)	-0.00319 (0.008)	-0.0162* (0.008)	0.0653*** (0.01)	0.0104*** (0.003)
Personal concern	-0.106*** (0.02)	-0.0512*** (0.009)	0.0100 (0.009)	0.100*** (0.01)	0.0463*** (0.007)
Country concern	-0.111*** (0.01)	-0.0314*** (0.009)	0.0314*** (0.008)	0.0745*** (0.006)	0.0360*** (0.005)
Age	0.00027 (0.0003)	0.00010 (0.0001)	-0.00008 (0.00009)	-0.00022 (0.0002)	-0.00006 (0.00007)
Sex	-0.0120 (0.008)	0.0179** (0.007)	0.0138*** (0.005)	-0.0139** (0.006)	-0.00576** (0.002)
Education	-0.0243*** (0.005)	-0.0131*** (0.005)	-0.00416 (0.004)	0.0264*** (0.006)	0.0152*** (0.002)
Income	-0.0112* (0.006)	0.00019 (0.003)	-0.00366 (0.004)	0.0162*** (0.005)	-0.00155 (0.002)
Left-wing	-0.0695*** (0.01)	-0.0202** (0.01)	-0.00420 (0.008)	0.0730*** (0.01)	0.0209*** (0.005)
Right-wing	0.0403*** (0.01)	0.0142*** (0.005)	-0.0115*** (0.004)	-0.0334*** (0.01)	-0.00961*** (0.003)
Center	-0.0620*** (0.02)	-0.00266 (0.01)	0.00333 (0.01)	0.0627*** (0.009)	-0.00137 (0.005)
Religious	-0.0125 (0.01)	0.0239*** (0.009)	0.00823 (0.007)	-0.0104 (0.007)	-0.00930*** (0.002)
Big city resident	-0.0218*** (0.007)	-0.00769*** (0.003)	0.00623*** (0.002)	0.0181*** (0.006)	0.00519*** (0.002)
Partner	0.00546 (0.006)	0.00193 (0.002)	-0.00156 (0.002)	-0.00452 (0.005)	-0.00130 (0.002)
Child	0.0219*** (0.005)	-0.00946* (0.006)	-0.00471 (0.005)	-0.00664 (0.006)	-0.00112 (0.003)
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	6,124	6,765	5,756	5,865	1,072

N = 25,582. McFadden adjusted $R^2 = 0.4198$. Standard errors in parentheses.

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

An individual who feels they belong to the lowest social classes will be 7.23% more likely to be strongly unwilling to pay much higher taxes, compared to an identical individual who considers themselves to be middle class.

A.3 Marginal effects of WTP higher prices with categorical income

Table A.3 contains all results for being willing or not to pay much higher prices to protect the environment, and highlights effects of income when considered as categorical. Indeed, household income can have non-linear or mixed effects, as shown in the literature.

Table A.3: Marginal effects of social status, proactive behavior and categorical income on WTP higher prices to protect the environment.

WTP_{price}	1. Very unwilling	2. Unwilling	3. Neutral	4. Willing	5. Very willing
Low social status	0.0635*** (0.009)	0.0157* (0.009)	-0.0335*** (0.006)	-0.0388*** (0.008)	-0.00696* (0.004)
Median social status	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
High social status	-0.0176*** (0.005)	-0.0242*** (0.006)	-0.0275*** (0.006)	0.0543*** (0.007)	0.0150*** (0.006)
Prosocial orientation	-0.0487*** (0.009)	-0.0198*** (0.006)	-0.0315*** (0.006)	0.0771*** (0.01)	0.0229*** (0.004)
Low Income	0.00896** (0.004)	0.00608** (0.002)	-0.000648** (0.0003)	-0.0105** (0.004)	-0.00390** (0.002)
Median Income	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
High Income	-0.0263*** (0.007)	-0.000889 (0.005)	-0.00968* (0.005)	0.0383*** (0.005)	-0.00140 (0.003)
Personal concern	-0.0863*** (0.01)	-0.0676*** (0.009)	-0.0234*** (0.007)	0.114*** (0.009)	0.0636*** (0.008)
Country concern	-0.0788*** (0.008)	-0.0430*** (0.008)	-0.00240 (0.008)	0.0826*** (0.007)	0.0416*** (0.005)
Age	0.0000686 (0.0002)	0.0000518 (0.0002)	-0.0000019 (0.000007)	-0.0000868 (0.0003)	-0.0000318 (0.0001)
Sex	-0.0119** (0.005)	0.0134*** (0.005)	0.00765 (0.006)	-0.00419 (0.006)	-0.00501* (0.003)
Education	-0.0152*** (0.004)	-0.0114*** (0.004)	-0.0163*** (0.005)	0.0294*** (0.005)	0.0136*** (0.002)
Left-wing	-0.0400*** (0.007)	-0.0302*** (0.005)	0.00111*** (0.0003)	0.0506*** (0.009)	0.0185*** (0.003)
Right-wing	0.0108 (0.007)	0.00818 (0.006)	-0.000299 (0.0003)	-0.0137 (0.009)	-0.00501 (0.003)
Center	-0.0424*** (0.01)	-0.0194* (0.01)	-0.00887 (0.008)	0.0609*** (0.01)	0.00977** (0.004)
Religious	0.00440 (0.004)	0.00332 (0.003)	-0.000122 (0.0001)	-0.00556 (0.006)	-0.00204 (0.002)
Big city resident	-0.00906* (0.005)	-0.00685* (0.004)	0.000251 (0.0002)	0.0115* (0.007)	0.00420* (0.002)
Partner	0.00421 (0.003)	0.00318 (0.003)	-0.000117 (0.0001)	-0.00533 (0.004)	-0.00195 (0.002)
Child	0.0214*** (0.005)	-0.000131 (0.005)	-0.00176 (0.007)	-0.0168*** (0.006)	-0.00278 (0.004)
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observation	3,915	5,665	6,228	8,403	1,506

N = 25,717. McFadden adjusted $R^2 = 0.4305$. Standard errors in parentheses.

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

An individual who feels they belong to the lowest social classes will be 6.29% more likely to be strongly unwilling to pay much higher prices, compared to an identical individual who considers themselves to be middle class.

A.4 Marginal effects of WTP higher prices with less aggregated Social status

Table A.4 presents all marginal effects of being willing or not to pay much higher prices to protect the environment, with a less aggregated social status : in five classes rather than in three.

Table A.4: Marginal effects estimates with less aggregated Social Status variable.

WTP_{price}	1. Very unwilling	2. Unwilling	3. Neutral	4. Willing	5. Very willing
Bottom Social Status	0.110*** (0.01)	0.0132 (0.01)	-0.0640*** (0.01)	-0.0630*** (0.008)	0.00381 (0.009)
Low Social Status	0.0495*** (0.009)	0.0169* (0.009)	-0.0241*** (0.007)	-0.0310*** (0.009)	-0.0113*** (0.003)
Median social status	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
High Social Status	-0.0227*** (0.005)	-0.0189*** (0.007)	-0.0232*** (0.006)	0.0529*** (0.007)	0.0118* (0.006)
Top Social Status	0.0120 (0.01)	-0.0639*** (0.01)	-0.0590*** (0.01)	0.0732*** (0.02)	0.0377*** (0.007)
Prosocial orientation	-0.0483*** (0.009)	-0.0199*** (0.006)	-0.0324*** (0.005)	0.0776*** (0.011)	0.0230*** (0.004)
Personal concern	-0.0865*** (0.01)	-0.0677*** (0.009)	-0.0232*** (0.007)	0.114*** (0.009)	0.0630*** (0.008)
Country concern	-0.0788*** (0.009)	-0.0424*** (0.008)	-0.00305 (0.009)	0.0826*** (0.007)	0.0416*** (0.005)
Age	0.0000720 (0.0002)	0.0000547 (0.0002)	-0.0000020 (0.000007)	-0.0000913 (0.0003)	-0.0000334 (0.0001)
Sex	-0.0111** (0.005)	0.0127** (0.005)	0.00726 (0.006)	-0.00411 (0.006)	-0.00481* (0.003)
Education	-0.0151*** (0.004)	-0.0113** (0.004)	-0.0161*** (0.005)	0.0288*** (0.005)	0.0136*** (0.002)
Income	-0.0162*** (0.005)	-0.00441 (0.003)	-0.00556* (0.003)	0.0258*** (0.003)	0.000314 (0.002)
Left-wing	-0.0397*** (0.007)	-0.0301*** (0.005)	0.00110*** (0.0003)	0.0503*** (0.009)	0.0184*** (0.003)
Right-wing	0.0111 (0.007)	0.00843 (0.006)	-0.000309 (0.0003)	-0.0141 (0.009)	-0.00515 (0.003)
Center	-0.0422*** (0.01)	-0.0189* (0.01)	-0.00876 (0.008)	0.0597*** (0.01)	0.0101** (0.004)
Religious	0.00452 (0.004)	0.00343 (0.003)	-0.000126 (0.0001)	-0.00573 (0.006)	-0.00210 (0.002)
Big city resident	-0.00901* (0.005)	-0.00684* (0.004)	0.000251 (0.0002)	0.0114* (0.007)	0.00418* (0.002)
Partner	0.00458 (0.003)	0.00347 (0.003)	-0.000127 (0.0001)	-0.00580 (0.004)	-0.00212 (0.002)
Child	0.0218*** (0.005)	-0.000247 (0.005)	-0.00227 (0.007)	-0.0171*** (0.006)	-0.00222 (0.004)
Control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observation	3,915	5,665	6,228	8,403	1,506

N = 25,717. McFadden adjusted $R^2 = 0.4312$. Standard errors in parentheses.

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

An individual who feels they belong to the lowest social classes will be 11% more likely to be strongly unwilling to pay much higher prices, compared to an identical individual who considers themselves to be middle class.

A.5 Marginal effects of WTP by cutting in standards of living

Table A.5 presents the marginal effects of being willing or not to cut in the standards of living to protect the environment.

Table A.5: Marginal effects of all variables on willingness to pay by cutting in living standards.

<i>WTPStandards</i>	1. Very unwilling	2. Unwilling	3. Neutral	4. Willing	5. Very willing
Low social status	0.0464*** (0.007)	0.0133 (0.008)	-0.0377*** (0.006)	-0.0237*** (0.009)	0.00155 (0.004)
Median social status	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
High social status	0.00193 (0.007)	-0.00108 (0.008)	-0.0224*** (0.006)	0.00516 (0.008)	0.0164*** (0.005)
Prosocial orientation	-0.0524*** (0.01)	-0.0275*** (0.008)	-0.0320*** (0.007)	0.0844*** (0.01)	0.0275*** (0.005)
Personal concern	-0.0788*** (0.02)	-0.0554*** (0.01)	-0.0370*** (0.009)	0.111*** (0.01)	0.0600*** (0.01)
Country concern	-0.0746*** (0.007)	-0.0554*** (0.005)	-0.00157** (0.001)	0.0909*** (0.008)	0.0408*** (0.004)
Age	0.000447** (0.0002)	0.000332** (0.0001)	0.00000938* (0.000005)	-0.000544** (0.0002)	-0.000244** (0.0001)
Sex	-0.00875** (0.004)	-0.00650** (0.003)	-0.000184* (0.0001)	0.0107** (0.005)	0.00478** (0.002)
Education	-0.0128*** (0.003)	-0.00949*** (0.002)	-0.000268** (0.0001)	0.0156*** (0.003)	0.00698*** (0.001)
Income	-0.00534 (0.004)	0.00639** (0.003)	-0.00825*** (0.003)	0.0163*** (0.005)	-0.00912*** (0.002)
Left-wing	-0.0372*** (0.008)	-0.0276*** (0.006)	-0.000782** (0.0004)	0.0453*** (0.009)	0.0203*** (0.004)
Right-wing	0.0246*** (0.009)	0.0183*** (0.007)	0.000517 (0.0003)	-0.0300*** (0.01)	-0.0134** (0.005)
Center	-0.0238*** (0.007)	-0.0177*** (0.005)	-0.000501** (0.0002)	0.0290*** (0.009)	0.0130*** (0.004)
Religious	-0.00599 (0.008)	0.0127* (0.007)	0.00346 (0.006)	0.00574 (0.009)	-0.0159*** (0.004)
Big city resident	0.00271 (0.006)	0.00201 (0.004)	0.0000569 (0.0001)	-0.00330 (0.007)	-0.00148 (0.003)
Partner	-0.00615* (0.003)	-0.00457* (0.002)	-0.000129* (0.0001)	0.00749* (0.004)	0.00336* (0.002)
Child	0.0125*** (0.004)	-0.00574 (0.006)	-0.0205*** (0.004)	0.0133** (0.006)	0.000440 (0.003)
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	3,872	5,606	6,141	8,344	1,492

N = 25,455. McFadden adjusted $R^2 = 0.4290$. Standard errors in parentheses.

***, **, and * represent significances at 1%, 5%, and 10%.

An individual who feels they belong to the lowest social classes will be 4.64% more likely to be strongly unwilling to cut in their standard of living, compared to an identical individual who considers themselves to be middle class.

A.6 Role of beliefs on social status

Table A.6 presents the marginal effects of being willing or not pay much higher prices to protect the environment according to the individual's beliefs of their social status. A negative residual corresponds to the individual's perception that their stated social status is inferior than their objective computed social status.

Table A.6: Marginal effects of beliefs about social status and proactive behavior on WTP higher prices to protect the environment.

WTP_{prices}	1. Very unwilling	2. Unwilling	3. Neutral	4. Willing	5. Very willing
40% negative beliefs	0.0378*** (0.007)	0.0145** (0.006)	-0.0309*** (0.007)	-0.0152** (0.006)	-0.00619 (0.004)
20% median beliefs	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level	Reference level
40% positive beliefs	-0.0174*** (0.004)	-0.0164*** (0.006)	-0.0348*** (0.009)	0.0534*** (0.007)	0.0151*** (0.005)
Prosocial orientation	-0.0492*** (0.009)	-0.0197*** (0.006)	-0.0319*** (0.005)	0.0774*** (0.01)	0.0234*** (0.004)
Personal concern	-0.0867*** (0.01)	-0.0673*** (0.009)	-0.0237*** (0.007)	0.114*** (0.009)	0.0638*** (0.009)
Country concern	-0.0791*** (0.008)	-0.0424*** (0.008)	-0.00393 (0.009)	0.0835*** (0.007)	0.0419*** (0.005)
Age	0.0000891 (0.0002)	0.0000667 (0.0002)	-0.0000022 (0.000006)	-0.000112 (0.0003)	-0.0000412 (0.0001)
Sex	-0.0116** (0.005)	0.0135*** (0.005)	0.00752 (0.006)	-0.00420 (0.006)	-0.00519* (0.003)
Education	-0.0259*** (0.003)	-0.0194*** (0.003)	0.000627*** (0.0002)	0.0327*** (0.004)	0.0120*** (0.002)
Income	-0.0255*** (0.005)	-0.00648** (0.003)	-0.00469 (0.003)	0.0342*** (0.003)	0.00238 (0.002)
Left-wing	-0.0405*** (0.007)	-0.0303*** (0.005)	0.000981*** (0.0004)	0.0511*** (0.009)	0.0187*** (0.003)
Right-wing	0.0105 (0.008)	0.00786 (0.006)	-0.000254 (0.0002)	-0.0133 (0.009)	-0.00485 (0.003)
Center	-0.0420*** (0.01)	-0.0193* (0.01)	-0.00989 (0.008)	0.0611*** (0.01)	0.0102** (0.004)
Religious	0.00378 (0.004)	0.00283 (0.003)	-0.0000915 (0.0001)	-0.00477 (0.006)	-0.00175 (0.002)
Big city resident	-0.00944* (0.006)	-0.00707* (0.004)	0.000229 (0.0002)	0.0119* (0.007)	0.00436* (0.003)
Partner	0.00348 (0.003)	0.00261 (0.003)	-0.0000844 (0.0001)	-0.00440 (0.004)	-0.00161 (0.002)
Child	0.0217*** (0.005)	0.0000647 (0.005)	-0.00191 (0.007)	-0.0177*** (0.006)	-0.00219 (0.004)
Control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	3,915	5,665	6,228	8,403	1,506

N = 25,717. McFadden adjusted $R^2 = 0.4299$. Standard errors in parentheses.

***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

An individual who has a negative belief, i.e. who undervalued themselves, will be 3.78% more likely to be strongly unwilling to pay much higher prices, compared to an identical individual who considers themselves accurately.